

These results indicate that supplementary pollination during the pollen grain spreading peak of the male parent had more effect on seed yield than the previous method of pollinating each half hour from maternal flowering to end of flowering of male parent. Seed set increased more than 7.6% and seed yield 8%.

We devised a new technique for supplementary pollination. A nylon rope 0.4 cm in diameter is pulled at 1 m/s along the length of the plots, to scatter pollen grains during the spreading peak. This is carried out two times for each peak, at a 15-min interval, in double peaks; 3-4 times for only one peak. ■

Flowering curves of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. Lingling, Hunan, China, 1987-89.

F₁ fertility in indica/japonica crosses

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Low F₁ fertility in crosses of indica and japonica is still a problem. In 1988, we tested the F₁ fertility of two sets of combinations under irrigated conditions. One set was a direct japonica/indica cross (a native japonica variety was crossed with an exotic indica); the other was a modified japonica/indica cross (an advanced line or native japonica variety de-

rived from indica/ japonica was crossed with a japonica or an indica parent).

Modified japonicalindica crosses showed significantly higher spikelet fertility (74.1-90.25%) than the typical japonica/indica cross (9.75-35.75%) (see table).

The sterility of F₁ hybrids in direct indica/japonica cross was reportedly the result of genic or cryptic structural hybridity between chromosomes of the

indica and japonica varieties. We infer that the higher fertility in the modified japonicalindica crosses must be the result of the effectiveness of the advanced lines or native japonica varieties used as bridge parents. They presumably carry either dominant genes, to neutralize the effects of recessive complementary lethal genes in the indica and/or japonica variety, or wide compatible genes, to overcome the hybrid sterility barrier. ■

Comparison of F₁ fertility in japonica/indica crosses. Wuhan, China, 1988.

Cross	Fertility (%)
<i>Direct japonica/indica</i>	
LK58/IR36	9.75
HLR4/IR36	16.46
Gh 4/IR28	35.35
105/TKM6	19.82
H857/TKM6	24.23
Mean (x ₂)	21.22
LSD	9.59
<i>Modified japonica/indica</i>	
607 ^a /Longfu 6 ^b	86.53
607/Bamboo rice ^c	90.25
6107 ^a /VN51 ^c	77.70
6107/857 ^b	87.00
HLRS ^b /GS1 ^c	86.37
HLR5/I 636 ^c	74.10
Mean (x ₁)	83.66
LSD	6.28
t = 13.01 > 1% level	

^a Advanced line. ^b Japonica variety derived from an indica/ japonica cross. ^c Indica variety.

Use of male gametocide to induce complete male sterility in a partially male sterile rice

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Photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile rice (PGMSR) is also very sensitive to temperature. While photoperiod is relatively even from year to year, temperature is variable. This means a PGMSR grown in the summer can show variation in pollen sterility, making it unsuitable as female parent in hybrid seed production.

We evaluated a new indica PGMSR, CIS28-15, that was isolated from a B₉F₄ progeny of the cross Caloro/IR28. The critical stage of its sterility-transformation is about 20 Jul, with fertility-transformation 5 Sep under normal conditions in Xiangtan (29° N). But in 1989, male

sterility in the field was not complete between 20 Jul and 15 Aug because the air temperature was unusually low (mean 23 °C) and fluctuated widely.

We sought to induce complete pollen sterility by spraying the male gametocide (CH₃As O₃Zn.H₂O) in 30, 40, 50, and 60 ppm concentrations on the leaves of CIS28-15 at 5 d before heading. Other plants of CIS28-15 were sprayed with plain water. The experiment had four replications, with 20 hills of 1 plant each.

Initiation of panicle primordium starts about 30 d before heading. From 20 Jul to 15 Aug, we recorded the heading date of every panicle, including those of the main shoot and all tillers, to infer the development stage of each panicle when the plant was sprayed with the male gametocide. Observations on pollen and spikelet fertility were made on bagged panicles and open-pollinated panicles.

The results indicated the following (see table):

Panicle development stage at time of spraying	Pollen fertility (%)					Spikelet fertility (%) on bagged panicle					Seed set on open-pollinated panicle				
	30	40	50	60	Check	30	40	50	60	Check	30	40	50	60	V20A
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	(check)
Branch differentiation	7.5	7.8	6.0	7.1	7.7	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.39					
Spikelet differentiation	3.5	3.1	3.1	3.5	7.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.3					
Reduction division of pollen mother cell	1.1	1.1	0	0	7.4	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.4			9.8	9.8	11.4
Pollen wall (exine) formation	0	0	0	0	7.3	0	0	0	0	1.4	10.3	10.1	10.2	10.0	11.0

- At branch differentiation stage, there was no difference in pollen fertility and self-fertilization between materials sprayed with the male gametocide and check. The male gametocide had no effect on the young panicle.
- At the spikelet differentiation stage, there was obvious difference, but effectiveness was low.

- At the reduction division stage of the pollen mother cell, effectiveness of 30 and 40 ppm spray was best.
 - At the pollen exine stage, all spray levels were effective, with no fertile pollen in the anther and no self-fertilization.
- We concluded the effect of low temperature can be controlled and complete

pollen sterility of CIS28-15 maintained by spraying with the male gametocide 5 d before heading, at the pollen exine stage. A second treatment may be necessary to sterilize all tillers at the appropriate development stage.

The treatment does not affect the outcrossing rate of CIS28-15. ■

Yield potential

Genetic nature of high-density rice grain

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In 1988 dry season, we studied the genetic nature of HD grain production using the parents, F₁, F₂, and two backcrosses of Rewa 353-5/IR56, IR56/Rewa 353, and Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2. Single seeds of the six generations were sown separately in 4-liter pots containing 3 kg of Maahas clay soil (Andaqueptic Haplaquolls) mixed with 4 g ammonium

sulfate, 2 g single superphosphate, and 2 g muriate of potash. The number of HD grains produced on primary branches (Pb) and secondary branches (Sb) of the panicles was determined by salt solution.

Mean data from 15 plants of parents and F₁, 50 plants of backcrosses, and 100 plants of F₂ were used for analysis. The HD grain index (HDI) was calculated as the number of HD grains divided by the number of spikelets per plant.

The parents differed significantly in number of HD grains and HDI (Table 1). Rewa 353-5 had the most HD grains (1,088) but IR28211-43-1-1-2 had the highest HDI (53.2%). Although heterobeltiosis for number of HD grains was 113% for F₁ of IR56/Rewa 353 and 50%

for Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2, the HDI of Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2 was very close to that of the higher parent because of the higher number of spikelets. The HDI of Rewa 353-5/IR56 was much lower than the mid-parent value.

In all crosses, mean HD grain was lower in the F₂ than in the F₁ and the better parent. Backcrosses with the better parent produced more HD grains than backcrosses with the lower parent. The F₂ plants produced more than the better parent.

These results indicate scope for selecting of parents and the possibility of getting heterotic lines from such crosses.

Estimates of gene effects (Table 2) indicate highly significant additive and

Table 1. Mean HD grains in 6 generations of Rewa 353-5/IR56 (1), IR56/Rewa 353 (2), and Rewa 353-4/IR28211-43-1-1-2 (3). IRRI, 1988.

Generation	HD grain/plant (no.)									High density grain index		
	Primary branch			Secondary branch			Total HD grain (no.)					
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
P ₁	475p5.4	253p5.3	244p4.7	613p7.7	317p 7.1	399p9.4	1088	570	643	47.6	33.3	33.8
P ₂	253p5.3	273p8.2	530p5.3	317p7.1	419p10.8	398p6.1	570	692	928	33.3	25.9	53.2
F ₁	228p4.4	704p5.7	731p5.0	357p6.8	771p 8.7	719p3.8	585	1475	1450	23.1	53.6	54.7
F ₂	182p4.1	248p4.6	411p7.3	204p5.7	359p 7.2	440p7.5	386	607	851	18.3	27.4	38.9
BC ₁	274p4.5	203p8.8	173p4.6	376p9.7	220p12.8	215p7.2	650	423	388	27.9	17.5	18.8
BC ₂	9p0.6	389p5.9	695p9.2	10p0.8	595p 8.6	561p8.9	19	984	1256	1.0	41.1	62.7